

Terpenoids: Part XXX. Syntheses of 1(7), 4(8)-*p*-menthadiene and γ -terpineol

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4-Isopropylidene cyclohexanone, prepared through an unambiguous sequence of reactions, when subjected to Wittig's reaction with methylene phosphorane and to Grignard reaction with CH_3MgI affords the syntheses of 1(7), 4(8)-*p*-menthadiene and γ -terpineol respectively.

Vig *et al* have made an extensive use of Wittig¹ and modified Wittig² reactions in accomplishing the unambiguous syntheses of many terpenoids^{3,8}, and as a result it has been confirmed that with the aid of these procedures the position of the double bond in the isopropenyl and isopropylidene end groups of terpenic molecules is fixed beyond any doubt even under energetically unfavourable circumstances.

Another equally important method for the fixation of this double bond is the hydrogenolysis reaction⁹ of suitably constituted allylic carbinols with sodium and ethanol in liquid ammonia. Syntheses of some of the terpenoids executed through the utilization of this approach have been recently communicated^{10,11}. The present communication reports the syntheses of the title compounds through the application of above mentioned techniques.

1(7), 4(8)-*p*-menthadiene, a monoterpene hydrocarbon does not, occur in nature and has been recently reported by Mitzner and Lemberg¹² as one of the products from the pyrolysis of γ -triphenyl acetate. These authors assigned constitution (1) for this new hydrocarbon on the basis of its infra-red and n.m.r. spectra¹². The present investigations record a synthetic proof for this structure achieved through the following sequence of reactions.

2-Carbomethoxy-4, 4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexanone¹³ (II), on alkaline hydrolysis followed by decarboxylation with copper powder furnished, 4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexanone (III), m.p. 70-72° (Lit.¹⁴ m.p. 72-73°). The ketal-ketone (III) was submitted to the

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modified Wittig reaction² with ethyl α -diethylphosphono-propionate in presence of sodium hydride to give 4, 1-carboethoxyethylidene-1, 1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (IV). The unsaturated ester (IV) was reduced to the corresponding alcohol (V) with lithium aluminium hydride.

The allylic carbinol (V) when subjected to hydrogenolysis with⁹ sodium and ethanol in liquid ammonia afforded, after chromatography over alumina, 4-isopropylidene-1, 1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (VI). During this reaction, the formation of the single isopropylidene-isomer (VI) by the protonation of the intermediate carbanion, is supported by the absence of the infra-red bands in the region 850-800 cm⁻¹—(isopropenyl) and the presence of only a single spot in thin layer chromatography of this compound.

The ketal (VI) was deketalised in acetone solution in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid to secure the ketone (VII), a yellow *DNP*, m.p. 129-30° (Lit.¹⁵ m.p. 130-131.5°). The ketone (VII) was submitted to Wittig reaction¹ with methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide to give 1-methylene-4-isopropylidene-cyclohexane (1).

The synthetic hydrocarbon, after purification over alumina, showed characteristic I.R. peaks at 1650, 888 cm⁻¹ ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ R_2 \end{matrix} = CH_2$), 1240 cm⁻¹ ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ \diagdown \\ C=C \\ \diagup \\ R_2 \end{matrix}$). Mitzner and Lemberg¹² reports peaks at 886 cm⁻¹ ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ R_2 \end{matrix} = CH_2$), 1237 cm⁻¹ ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ \diagdown \\ C \\ \diagup \\ R_2 \end{matrix} = C \begin{matrix} R_1 \\ \diagdown \\ \\ \diagup \\ R_2 \end{matrix}$). Moreover the absence of gem-dimethyl split (1375-1385 cm⁻¹) as noted by these authors is also confirmed in the synthetic product.

The n.m.r. spectrum of (1) indicates the following (in T values, tetramethylsilane as an internal standard, 10.000) (a) $T = 5.38$, singlet, (2 hydrogens); (b) $T = 7.81$, allylic methylene, singlet, 8 hydrogens; (c) $T = 8.30$, (singlet) 6 hydrogens. These values of n.m.r. spectrum confirm the constitution (1).

As the ketone (VII) has been prepared in the pure form through an unambiguous route, we repeated the experiments of McPherson and Frank¹⁵ with CH₃MgI on this compound, to synthesise γ -terpineol (VIII).

15. Robert L. Frank and James B. McPherson, (Jr.) *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1387.

The synthetic alcohol (VIII) showed I.R. peaks at 3460 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1380 cm^{-1} (C-Me). It solidified on chilling and the purified product melted at $64.66.5^\circ$ (Lit.¹⁵ m.p. 63.67°).

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Carbomethoxy-4, 4-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexanone (II): This compound was prepared according to the procedure reported in the literature¹³.

4,4-Ethylenedioxy-cyclohexanone (III): The β -keto ester (II, 10 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of KOH (10 g.), methanol (75 ml.) and water (60 ml.) for 10 hours. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure and to the residue was added sufficient cold water and ether (100 ml.). The reaction mixture was neutralised with ice-cold HCl and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed thoroughly with cold water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled under vacuum with copper powder to yield 5.4 g. (75%) of (III), b.p. $115^\circ/5\text{ mm.}$ Shining white crystals, m.p. 70.72° . ν_{max} 1720 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal). (Found C, 60.99; H, 7.70, Cal. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$: C, 61.51; H, 7.75%).

4, 1'-Carbomethoxy ethylidene-1, 1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (IV): Sodium hydride (1.5 g.) was placed in diethyleneglycol dimethyl ether (40 ml.). Ethyl α -diethylphosphoropropionate (5.2 g.) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring and the solution was stirred until the gas evolution had ceased. To the resultant yellow solution was then added (III) (4g.) slowly below 25° . After the addition, the solution was further stirred for 1 hr. and then refluxed for half an hour. The product was extracted with ether after decomposing with a large excess of water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The residue furnished on distillation the α, β -unsaturated ester (IV), (5.4 g., 71.8%); b.p. $160^\circ/8\text{ mm.}$; η_D^{20} 1.4620 (Found: C, 64.82; H, 8.23. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.98; H, 8.39%).

4, 1'-Hydroxymethylethylidene-1, 1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (V): To a suspension of LiAlH_4 (250 mg.) in anhydrous ether (75 ml.) was added slowly with stirring the α, β -unsaturated ester (IV, 5 g.) in ether (30 ml.) at such rate so as to keep ether at a gentle reflux. After the mixture have been stirred for an additional 2 hours, a small volume of ethyl acetates was added followed by sodium sulphate solution. The product was extracted with ether, dried (Na_2SO_4), evaporated and distilled under reduced pressure to provide allylic alcohol (V) as a thick oil; b.p. $145.50^\circ/4\text{ mm.}$; yield 3.3 g. (86%); η_D^{20} 1.5170. I.R. absorption peaks at $3460, 1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (-OH) and 1050 cm^{-1} (ketal). (Found: C, 66.28; H, 8.98. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.64; H, 9.15%).

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected, Microanalysis by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

4-*Isopropylidene-1, 1-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane* (VI): To a well stirred mixture of the allylic carbinol (V, 3 g.) in absolute ethanol (8 ml.) and anhydrous liquid ammonia (150 ml.) was added sodium metal (2 g.) in small pieces during 20 minutes. The contents were stirred for 3 hours more and excess of ammonia was evaporated. The residual solid cake was decomposed with cold water and the material was taken up in ether. The extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent having been expelled, the residue was passed through an alumina column when (VI) was obtained on elution with petroleum ether (40-60°, 50 ml.). It was further purified by distillation, b.p. 117-120°/6 mm.; yield 2.1 g. (73%); η_D^{25} 1.4805; Rf=0.85 (Ether, petroleum ether, ethyl acetate; 5:2) on silica gel. I.R. absorption peaks at 1460, 1375 cm^{-1} (C-Me); 1120, 1040 cm^{-1} (ketal) and no absorption at 850-900 cm^{-1} (isopropenyl). (Found: C, 71.88; H, 9.85. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 72.49; H, 9.96%).

4-*Isopropylidene-cyclohexanone* (VII): The ketal (VI, 1.82 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of acetone (40 ml.) and 10% HCL (15 ml.) and the contents were stirred well for two hours at room temperature. The resulting mixture was diluted with saturated sodium chloride solution (50 ml.) and the product was isolated with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was evaporated and the residue on distillation provided 1.25 g. (82%) of the ketone (VII); b.p. 105-108°/10 mm.; η_D^{25} 1.4760. I.R. absorption peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1375 (C-Me). (Found: C, 77.83; H, 10.05. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.21; H, 10.21%).

The ketone (VII) formed a yellow 2:4-DNP which after crystallisation from ethanol, melted at 129-30°. (Found: N, 17.71, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires N, 17.60%).

1-*Methylene-4-isopropylidene-cyclohexane* (I): Dimethylsulphanyl sodium was prepared from NaH (350 mg.) and dimethylsulphoxide (3.5 ml.). To the stirred solution was added at 0° a solution of 2.6 g. of methyltriphenyl phosphonium iodide in 7 ml. of sulphoxide. The resulting orange brown mixture was stirred for 10 minutes at room temperature and a solution of 500 mg. of the ketone (VII) in T.H.F. (5 ml.) was added dropwise. The contents were stirred and heated for half an hour at 50° and left overnight at room temperature. The mixture was diluted with cold water and the material was taken up in petroleum ether (40-60°). After drying and solvent removal, the residue was chromatographed over alumina (20 g.) when elution with petroleum ether (40-60°, 25 ml.) afforded the pure hydrocarbon (I) which was then distilled, b.p. 90-95°/15 mm.; yield 415 mg. (83%) η_D^{28} 1.4750.

I.R. spectrum of (I) showed prominent bands at 3050, 2900, 1650, 1425, 1365, 1240, 1190, 980, 888 and 720 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. gives signals at: $T=8.30$, $\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array} \right\} \text{C}=\text{C}$; 7.81, allylic methylene; 5.38, $>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$. (Found: C, 87.75; H, 11.76. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

1-*Methyl-1-hydroxy-4-isopropylidene-cyclohexane* (VIII): Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (300 mg.) and methyl iodide (2 g.) in anhydrous ether (50 ml.). This was cooled in ice-cold water and the ketone (VII, 400 mg.) in anhydrous ether (10 ml.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition was complete, the contents were left overnight and thereafter refluxed for about an hour to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted a few times with ether.

The total ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The residue on distillation gave γ -terpineol (VIII) as a colourless material, b.p. 85°/5 mm. It crystallised out on chilling; m.p. 64-66.5°; yield 320 mg. (70%). (Found: C, 77.51; H, 11.58. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₈O: C, 77.92; H, 11.68%).

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